

BIG EARTH DATA AND ADVANCED PROCESSING TECHNIQUES FOR MONITORING WATER QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

Mapping Human Exposure to Risky Environmental Conditions is key to quantify the vulnerability of population and economic assets. In order to develop novel tools, implementing the use of information layers from current and future Earth Observation (EO) missions is necessary. The EOxposure project that has been created and funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program covers this purpose. Several topics involving human exposure to environmental risks are being studied, including water quality and pollution, which is addressed in this paper.

The high productivity of biomass registered in eutrophic water bodies, leads to qualitative and quantitative changes in the phytoplankton community, resulting in massive algae blooms. This research work proposes a methodology that takes advantage of the temporal and spectral resolution of Sentinel-2 (S2) for monitoring eutrophic reservoir. Specifically, it uses large temporal series of S2 images and advanced data mining techniques to study the turbid and productive water of San Roque reservoir, Argentina. The spatial patterns and the temporal tendencies of these aquatic indicators are analysed and evaluated in order to assess their contribution to water quality models and a local water management program.

Index Terms— Eutrophication, phytoplankton, Sentinel-2, multitemporal, modeling, inland water

1. INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, water has been considered a renewable resource. However, sustained degradation of its quality has been observed in the last century in continental and oceanic systems due to the anthropogenic activities and climate changes. This global threat leads to changes in water supplies, extreme productivity of biomass and increase in eutrophication processes [1]. This high productivity of biomass in eutrophic water bodies results in changes in the phytoplankton community, facilitating the creation of algal blooms

[2]. These blooms are commonly the cause of changes in the water's color and odor as well as oxygen shortage and fish mortality. Furthermore, certain algae species can produce toxins that can cause harm to animals and humans using or drinking the water [3]. Traditionally, algal blooms are monitored using *in situ* measurements. However, during blooms events when the spatial distribution of phytoplankton biomass is high, conventional water sampling is insufficient to characterize the distribution of the algae. In these cases, satellite based multi-spectral imaging becomes an essential and effective monitoring tool [4]. Chlorophyll-a concentration [Chl-a] is the main indicator for algal bloom, however, retrieving this indicator and information regarding algae species using satellite remote sensing remained a challenge because of the low spatial and temporal resolutions of the sensors and because of the presence of many other optically active substances. One practical solution to overcome these difficulties is to integrate information from different sensors and platforms along large period of time. To demonstrate this capability, several advanced processing frameworks have been developed for supporting the water management of San Roque reservoir, Argentina, using big earth data. Specifically, the temporal behavior of [Chl-a] was characterized using MODIS-TERRA [5], the spatial and thermal behaviour of the lake with Landsat 5 and 8 data [6] and the temporal spectral changes of the water components using Sentinel 2 (S2) data [7]. In [8] the MODIS [Chl-a] series were modelled with Harmonic ANalysis of Time Series (HANTS) [9] to detect algae blooms while in [7] unmixing algorithms were used to extract spectral characteristics of the water components. In this work we extend and complement the spectral analysis using S2 with a method to obtain spatial and temporal information using large temporal series. The proposed method uses data mining techniques to extract temporal and spatial patterns combined with spatial indexes to determine the sources of pollution that lead to bloom events.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

San Roque reservoir (31° 22' 56" S, 64° 27' 56" W) is used as the main water supply for the city, Córdoba, for flooding control, hydroelectric energy and recreational activities. Anthropogenic activities around the lake are concentrated in the urban areas of the cities Carlos Paz (31° 24' 00" S, 64° 31' 00" W) and La Falda (31° 05' 00" S) where only limited sewage treatments are available. During summer time, when the population of these cities triples due to tourism, the number of algal blooms also increases.

Field data is collected and generated in the context of a monitoring program carried out by the Ministry of Water, Environment and Public Services of the province of Córdoba (Argentina) [6]. The monitoring stations shown in Fig. 1 were selected to evaluate the effect of the aeration system on the water quality. Three stations are located at the active part of the diffusers ("Zona A", "Zona B" and "Garganta"), one station at the centre of the lake ("Centro") and four stations near the entrance of the tributaries ("SAT 1", "SAT 2", "SAT 3" and "SAT 4"). Sampling, storage, preservation, and analysis of water samples were carried out according to the methodology proposed by the Standard Methods for Water and Wastewater [10].

All available Sentinel 2 A and B images of the area from launch till the end of August 2019 are considered in this research. In total we used 132 images, with less than 30% cover of clouds, automatically downloaded with module `i.sentinel.download` [11].

In this study we propose a monitoring scheme to integrate multitemporal S2 images with *in-situ* data in order to characterize the water quality over time and space. First, we selected all the field data coincident with S2 acquisition dates for the period 2016-2019. This resulted in the selection of nine dates, 19 measurements of [Chl-a] for modeling and 16 measurements for validation. Secondly, Pearson correlation analysis between field data and 3x3 pixels around the sampling points was calculated over all the S2 bands or over selected combinations (i.e. logarithms, indexes as NDVI, ratios for all the bands combinations). Bands or bands ratio that presented significant correlations (i.e. p value less than 0.01) were used to build linear models. The model with the highest r^2 and lowest Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values was chosen. Following, the retrieval of [Chl-a] was obtained using that linear model (developed in [12]), for each S2 image in the series (n=132). For the analysis, we also divided the results into hydrological years (August to July) and seasonal series. These temporal series were used to describe the spatial and temporal distribution of [Chl-a] in the water body by implementing the `r.series` module of GRASS GIS software [11]. Specifically, this module provides several statistical functions for extracting temporal behaviour of variables and obtaining their tendency along a selected period. Beside basic statistics functions this module also calculates the an-

nual linear regression R coefficient (slope) in order to extract a trend along the reservoir. To identify extreme events originated from algae blooms, we also defined a threshold using temporal-spatial statistics. For this, we calculated different percentiles to the spatial mean temporal series, derived for each date. Finally, we choose a value between the percentil 97 and 98, equal to 150 mg/m3. Even though it is consider a very high value ([13], [14]), the large range of [Chl-a] in the reservoir, makes it adequately to detect extreme events (i.e the mean minimum value in all the temporal series is 8.28 mg/m3 while the mean of the maximum values is 634.07 mg/m3).

Fig. 1. Map of San Roque reservoir showing the locations of sampling stations, diffusers, sewage treatment plant and tributary rivers.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Pearson analysis found a significant correlation of 0.789 between the concentration of [Chl-a] and S2 Band 8 (NIR: 0.842 nm) and S2 Band 4 (Red: 0.665 nm) ratio. Following these results, a linear regression model was developed using 60% of the modelling data according to:

$$[Chl - a] = -5.57 + 80.13 * band8/band4 \quad (1)$$

This model obtained an accuracy (R^2) of 0.77, a significant p-value < 0.0001 and a root mean square error (RMSE)

of 34.07 mg/m³ using the training data and a correlation of 0.82, a significant p-value < 0.0001 and RMSE of 13.53 mg/m³ using the validation data set. This results indicates that the 82% of the field data is explained by the model with more than 95% of confidence. The results using S2 data show better fit than previous model developed using any other EO sensor[6, 5].

A statistic analysis applied to the whole series shows an average [Chl-a] concentration of 50-65 ug/L, coincident with eutrophic conditions [15, 5]. High concentration values (> 750 mg/m³) are observed in areas that are directly influenced by the contributions of the tributaries in the basin, San Antonio at the south and Cosquin at the north.

Fig. 2. Yearly median of [Chl-a] in San Roque reservoir, calculated during hydrological year (August to July).

The results of the inter-annual analysis presented in Fig. 2 represents the temporal median in every pixel, taking from August until July next year, to include all summer (from December till March), since it is the most critical period for algae growth. Fig. 2 show large differences in spatial distribution during the years. In the years 2016/2017 and 2018/2019, the north part of the reservoir has been characterized by low [Chl-a] (< 40 mg/m³) while the shores and San Antonio area by high concentration values (> 60 mg/m³). On the other hand, in the year 2017/2018 almost the entire area of the lake has been characterized by high [Chl-a] (> 60 mg/m³). The water level fluctuation is the main reason for these inter-annual differences. The water level in 2017/2018 was very low in comparison to the hydrologic years 2018/2019 and 2016/2017 (Public data available at <https://www.cba.gov.ar/nivel-de-diques-y-embalses>).

Fig. 3 presents the seasonal-spatial variation of [Chl-a] within the reservoir. This spatial patterns were obtained by calculating the seasonal linear regression R coefficients (slopes) for each pixel in all dates per season in the temporal series. The results show that during summer and spring, the high positive slopes values (> 2) are mainly located in the northern part (i.e. entrances of Cosquin and Las Mojarras rivers) and eastern part (i.e. near the sewage treatment plant) of the reservoir and near the dam. This indicates that water quality has deteriorated in these areas during the warm season, when algae growth is the most prevalent. It is probably

Fig. 3. Seasonal linear regression R coefficients (slopes) of [Chl-a] for the temporal series (2016-2019).

caused by sewage treatment plant located near eastern coast, with the pipe inside water body (Fig. 1). During the warm season, when the tourist population triples, the pressure on the plant is high, resulting in failure in performing tertiary treatment of nutrient decantation. Also the northern part of the basin has suffered an important urban growth and there is no sewage treatment plant [16]. During the fall, only thin patterns of positive slopes values are observed in the center of the water body, while during the winter, the trend is changing and positive slope values are observed in all the area of the lake except near the main tributary rivers (San Antonio and Cosquin). This indicates that the growth of population in settlements near the lake is putting pressure on the water resources during the dry season and that the available sewage treatment is inadequate.

As we explained in section 2, we used a statistical threshold to identify extreme [Chl-a] values corresponding to algal blooms. We then calculated for each pixel the percentage of dates higher than this value and obtained a map of bloom occurrence. During maximum 12 days (i.e. 0-9 percents) between 2016 and 2019, the concentration of [Chl-a] was higher than the bloom threshold in most of the water body. Fig. 4 also shows that the frequency of this anomaly is higher in the entries of the main tributaries. Some high frequency can also be observed in the north-east coast of the basin and at the entry of the Los Chorrillos river in the south-west part of the reservoir. It should be noted that the frequencies of these

anomalies decrease near diffusers.

Fig. 4. Percentage of number of dates within [Chl-a] values were higher than 150 mg/m^3

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a first glimpse to the processes that affect eutrophic reservoirs and the effectiveness in using multitemporal S2 series to understand them. The spectral based empirical model and the multi-temp statistical analysis developed in this study allow to identify the tributary entries to San Roque as the main source of nutrients. Specifically, it shows that high content of organic matters carried from the watersheds by the flows of Cosquin and San Antonio Rivers are the main polluted sources of the reservoir. In addition, data mining tools as slope analysis and bloom threshold found very useful in identifying regions in the reservoir where water quality is improving or deteriorating. The high time frequency of S2 allows to provide early warning and information about the evolution of blooms events that are required for water management.

Nonetheless, a complex hydrological model is required to understand the spatial and temporal processes occur within eutrophic reservoir. Although the presented method uses large time series of EO data to train the predictive models, the solution only presents a holistic approach to this complex phenomenon. This because the [Chl-a] is only one indicator to measure the eutrophic level of water body and statistical analysis is only partially addressing this need. Therefore, future work will focus on enlarging the spatial and temporal model and integrate it with climatic, chemicals and anthropogenic variables for improving the available early warning system.

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